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CRITERIA AND INDICATORS FOR ASSESSING THE LEVEL OF FORMATION OF A NOBLE ATTITUDE TOWARDS WOMEN IN ADOLESCENTS

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Based on the lack of research, but the relevance of the topic of modern society, the study identifies and theoretically substantiates the criteria for the formation of a noble attitude and their respective indicators. The purpose of the study was to characterize the specific criteria and indicators of the formation of this attitude in adolescents on the basis of different approaches to the problem of the study. Based on the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature, the concept of "criterion" was clarified, which we understand as certain features that check the formation of a noble attitude towards women and analyze the dynamics of development, and the concept of "indicator", the formation of this concept for each of the criteria. Given that moral education includes a noble attitude towards women, analyzed a number of works by scientists to determine the general level of moral education, identified the criteria and indicators that characterize the concept, namely: cognitive-behavioral (characterized by completeness and depth of knowledge about the features of manifestation of a noble attitude and application of this knowledge in practice in everyday life), volitional (characterized by the formation of motives that will motivate the individual to selfless actions in accordance with the laws of ethics and morality, and meeting the needs of the individual, as well as experiencing certain emotions and feelings to representatives of the opposite sex), the person-reflexive (includes the nature of the identification of noble qualities of personality, accompanied by a desire to become even better). The defined criteria and indicators make it possible to assess the level of formation of noble attitudes in adolescents and analyze the dynamics of their changes during the experiment. The prospect of further scientific research is to study the dynamics of changes in the level of formation of a noble attitude in accordance with certain criteria and indicators with the help of selected diagnostic tools

Keywords: nobility, females, adolescents, upbringing, cognitive-behavioral, motivational-emotional, personal-reflexive

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1. Introduction

Ukraine is going through difficult times: the occupation of Crimea, military action in the east, so the education of a patriot becomes a priority, but moral values, traditions, customs are lost. Unfortunately, the modern young generation is increasingly demonstrating personal rudeness, cruelty, selfishness in society. There are especially cases of immorality, in particular in relation to the female half of humanity, among adolescent children. Educational reforms in the Ukrainian school necessitate the improvement of educational work. The formed system of values is the basis of the education of the individual, and therefore, the problem of determining the criteria and indicators is complex and remains the subject of research to this day. The problem of studying the criteria and indicators of the formation of a noble attitude towards women is insufficiently developed and little studied, and therefore, without them it is impossible to establish the level of formation of this concept in adolescents.

2. Literary review

Kobzarenko L.A. developed the criteria for the formation of valuable ideas among students, including a three-component structure. Each of components structure interconnections between themselves and one for one.

The level of upbringing is one of the most important orientations of characterization through the development of knowledge of the Ukrainian national decline, historical culture; the value of the motives of behavior; as well as through special features [1].

In the dissertation Stolyarenko O. V. also considered the criteria and indicators of the level of formation of values of a man. Selected criteria and their indicators allowed to characterize the moral development of the student, to present the nature of behavioral requirements to themselves in relation to other people [2].

Mr. Peterson studied the communication difficulties of children, deprived of parental care. The author believes that the full moral upbringing of a child requires examples of close family members, especially parents. Children, looking at them form their own worldview, learn to build their own patterns of behavior with others. Thus, the acquired knowledge and social experience, their implementation in practice will characterize the high level of education of the child [3]. Rohner R. studied the development of personality outside the family in his work, emphasizing that orphans have mental health problems, because they are deprived of positive emotional contact with mom or dad, so you should pay attention to the emotional sphere of the individual [4].

It should be noted, that a separate subject of the study that is criteria and indicators of the formation of a noble attitude towards women in adolescents has not yet been, and therefore, the study is relevant.

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The aim of this study is to substantiate the criteria and indicators for assessing the level of formation of a noble attitude towards women in adolescents.

To accomplish the aim, the following tasks have been set:

1. Selection of criteria for assessing the formation of a noble attitude towards women.

2. Substantiation of indicators according to the selected criteria.

4. Materials and methods

The following theoretical research methods were used to solve the set goal and reveal the tasks: analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature, systematization and generalization of views and achievements of scientists – to compare different approaches to criteria and indicators, related works on the topic. The source base was the work of Ukrainian and foreign scientists.

5. Research results and their discussion

To determine the criteria and indicators of the level of formation of a noble attitude towards women in adolescents, we analyze these concepts.

In the reference literature, the criterion is interpreted as a means of judgment that helps determine the effectiveness of something [5]; feature that is the basis for classification, evaluation of a phenomenon or object [6]; the level of achievement, at which the dynamics of development of someone or something is assessed [7].

In Kachur's research, M. interprets the concept of "criterion" as a "standard" for evaluating the phenomenon under study, which makes it possible to assess the dynamics of the phenomenon under study by identifying its positive and negative changes and, consequently, to determine the effectiveness of experimental work. [7]

A similar opinion is held in the work by Miroshnichenko V. The author defines a criterion as a set of certain features, with which you can analyze the quality and effectiveness of the work [8].

Zvereva I., Koval L., Frolov P. believe that a criterion is a feature that helps to evaluate, define or classify something [9].

The concept of "criterion" is revealed through the concept of "indicator", which should also be analyzed. Belt T. believes that the criterion of the formation of the object is determined by indicators, characterized by qualitative and quantitative features of the phenomenon under study [10].

Continuation of this idea is found in the work of Gaponchuk G., who believes that any criterion has a set of indicators that help to analyze and evaluate the formation of something [11].

In the reference literature, the concept of "indicator" is interpreted as data on the achievement of something or the results of an activity [12].

Shestopalyuk O. notes in his work that an indicator is a property that helps to identify the essential fea-

tures of the phenomenon under study, its presence, the dynamics of development [13].

The analysis of the scientific literature has shown that there is no unambiguous approach to the definition of concepts, and therefore, criteria are certain features that check the formation of a noble attitude towards women and analyze the dynamics of development, and indicators – a set of certain characteristics that determine the level of formation concept for each of the criteria.

To substantiate the criteria and indicators of the formation of a noble attitude towards women in adolescents, we will analyze the work, related to our issues. Noble attitude to women characterizes a man as a morally educated person, so we pay attention to the indicators and criteria of moral education of adolescents.

L. Bozhovych in her research singled out the following criteria: cognitive, emotional, behavioral. She believes that the set of knowledge, emotions, motives, and practical skills can characterize the level of education of the individual [14]. I. Sidanich singled out cognitive (moral knowledge, judgments, ideas), emotional-motivational (motives, emotions, needs), regulatory (degree of mastering moral knowledge in practice in everyday life), activity-practical (skills, habits), self-regulatory (ability personality to self-improvement) [15]

According to G. Soroka, the criteria of education should include knowledge of norms and rules of conduct, the presence of certain conditions, in which there is interaction with the environment and the presence of certain motives that guide the individual to real actions and deeds. [16].

Thus, the analysis of research on approaches to the definition of criteria and indicators shows that their number may be different. Taking into account the analyzed scientific sources and certain components of the researched problem, the following criteria were determined by the levels of formation of noble attitude to women: volitional, cognitive-behavioral, personal-reflexive (Table 1).

Very interesting is the opinion of Staub E. on the impact of society on human development, which is that the individual is motivated by selfless and consumer behavior in different ways in a particular environment [17].

The volitional criterion is characterized by motives, needs, emotions and feelings. Taken together, these indicators determine the behavior of a young person in relation to himself and others. Every action is accompanied by certain emotions and feelings. Moral knowledge, principles, norms, penetrating into the emotional and motivational sphere of the individual, form a worldview, values that serve to comply with certain behaviors in society. The nature of motivational actions becomes important: profiteering, selfless, material, etc. thus, the formation of altruistic, moral, communicative motives contribute to the establishment of interaction with women, the world around them and with themselves. Volitional criterion is characterized by the following indicators: the formation of altruistic, moral, communicative motives, needs, emotions (helping, protecting a woman, doing selfless deeds, satisfying the need to interact with the opposite sex, experiencing happy feelings, etc.); ability to control one's own emotional state. The high level of formation of motives, needs, emotional sphere, which

characterize the noble attitude to women, is accompanied by a system of acquired moral knowledge, readiness to use them in everyday life. The cognitive-behavioral criterion is revealed through the following indicators: the level of formation of the knowledge group on the idea of the peculiarities of the noble attitude to women from the past to the present; formation of communicative skills that characterize the adolescent's ability to find a com-

mon language and create a positive atmosphere of interaction with women of different ages; formation of empathic skills that help not only a friendly atmosphere of communication, but also help the individual to put himself in the place of a woman, to listen to her, to share with her her emotional experiences; formation of habits of moral and ethical behavior of treatment of females.

Table 1

Criteria and indicators for assessing the level of formation of a noble attitude towards women in adolescents

Criterion	Indicators
Volitional	– the formation of altruistic, moral, communicative motives, needs, emotions (feelings)
	– the ability to consciously control and adjust their own emotional reactions and states in any situation;
Cognitive-behavioral	– the level of formation of a group of knowledge about the manifestation and features of a noble attitude towards women
	– formation of communication skills
	– formation of empathic skills
	– the formation of habits
Personality-reflexive	– the formation of moral and ethical qualities: friendliness, respect, care, politeness, sensitivity, responsibility, activity;
	– formation of reflexive and evaluative skills
	– the desire for self-improvement

Thus, the high level of formation of cognitive-behavioral criteria will reflect the moral and ethical behavior in communication, actions with a woman, which indicates a willingness to take responsibility for their activities and the desire to self-educate the traits of a noble man.

No less important is the personality-reflexive criterion, which is represented by the following indicators: the nature of the identification of personal qualities, including friendliness, respect, care, politeness, sensitivity, responsibility, activity, which characterize the noble attitude towards women; the formation of reflexive and evaluative skills involves awareness of responsibility for their actions, behavior towards women and the desire for self-education and self-improvement.

5. Conclusions

1. Based on the analysis of different approaches to determining the criteria of education, the following criteria were identified: motivational, cognitive-behavioral and personal-reflexive;

2. Accordingly, the first criterion is characterized by altruistic, communicative, moral motives, needs and emotions, as well as the ability to control their own emotional state; cognitive-behavioral is represented by knowledge and formed by relevant skills; personality-reflexive includes the nature of the identification of personal qualities, the ability to analyze their activities and the desire for self-improvement.

Prospects for further research is to study the dynamics of changes in the level of formation of a noble attitude in accordance with certain criteria and indicators with the help of selected diagnostic tools.

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